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Research Paper

Development And Validation of Stability Indicating RP-HPLC Method For Quantification of Bisoprolol Fumarate and Telmisartan in Tablet Dosage Form

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ABSTRACT

Background: An anti-hypertensive drug having combination of Bisoprolol Fumarate and Telmisartan is used for the treatment of hypertension. Objective: This study aimed to develop, validate, and apply stability-indicating RP-HPLC method for quantitative estimation of Bisoprolol Fumarate and Telmisartan from Tablet dosage form. Method: Bisoprolol Fumarate and Telmisartan were separated by developing the Stability indicating RP-HPLC method on Hibar ODS C18 column (250 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 μm) in an isocratic mode using a mobile phase of Acetonitrile: 10 mM Phosphate Buffer (70: 30 v/v) with a flowrate of 1.0 ml/min and UV detection was carried out at 230 nm. Both drugs were subjected to stress conditions like acidic, basic, oxidative, and thermal degradation. Results: The proposed method is capable to separate and quantify the components from their combination. The proposed was able to detect the degradants of both drugs. The method was validated according to the guidelines described in the International Council for Harmonization guideline. Conclusion: The RP-HPLC method for assay of market formulations of Bisoprolol Fumarate and Telmisartan was successfully developed, validated, and found to be simple, accurate, precise, reproducible, sensitive, and robust and stability-indicating. Highlights: These findings suggested that the proposed RP-HPLC method can be employed in routine assay of Bisoprolol Fumarate and Telmisartan in combined formulation

INTRODUCTION

Bisoprolol fumarate is chemically 2-propanol,1-[4-[[2-(1-methylethoxy) ethoxy] methyl]

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phenoxy]-3-[(1-methylethyl) amino]-, (\pm)-, (E)-2-butenedioate. Bisoprolol fumarate is Cardioselective β_1 -adrenergic blocking agent. It is used as an antihypertensive drug. Bisoprolol Fumarate was used in the management of hypertension, angina pectoris, cardiac arrhythmias, myocardial infarction, and heart failure. Telmisartan is chemically 4'-{[4-methyl-

1H-benzimidazol-1-yl] methyl]-2-biphenyl-carboxylic acid. Telmisartan is an Angiotensin II receptor blockers (ARB). It is used as an antihypertensive drug. Telmisartan is used in the treatment of hypertension, heart attack, stroke, congestive heart failure (in patients who develop cough with ACE inhibitors). Also used in the treatment of diabetic nephropathy in hypertensive patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus.

Figure 1: Structure of Bisoprolol Fumarate

Figure 2: Structure of Telmisartan

Literature surveys revealed that two UV ^[1-2], four RP-HPLC ^[3-6] and two HPTLC ^[7-8] methods have been reported for determination of Bisoprolol fumarate and Telmisartan in combined tablet dosage form. This combination used for treatment

of hypertension. To our notice, so far, no stability-indicating RP-HPLC method has been reported for the determination of this combination. So, the estimation of the two drugs simultaneously can be done by stability-indicating RP-HPLC method.

Table 1: Instrumentation

Sr. no.	Instrument/Equipment	Specifications
1	HPLC	Make: Shimadzu Model: LC 2010 Column: Hibar ODS C ₁₈ (250 × 4.6 mm, 5 μm) Detector: UV Pump: Binary gradient high-pressure pump Software: LC solution
2	Applicator syringe	20 μL Hamilton, Bonaduz

3	UV-Visible Spectrometer	Make: Shimadzu Model: UV 1800 Detector: Photodiode Type: Double Beam spectrophotometer Software: U.V. Probe 2.42
4	Analytical Balance	Make: Mettler Toledo Sensitivity: 0.1 mg
5	Ultrasonic Cleaner	Electroquip

Reagents and Materials

Smt. S. M. Shah Pharmacy College, Amsaran, provided active ingredients of Bisoprolol Fumarate and Telmisartan, and analytical reagents like, HPLC grade-Methanol, Acetonitrile, Phosphate buffer and Water was used throughout the analysis. The Tablet dosage form containing Bisoprolol Fumarate 5 mg and Telmisartan 40 mg was procured from market.

Standard Stock solution preparation

- Bisoprolol Fumarate (BIS): Accurately weighed 10 mg of Bisoprolol Fumarate was dissolved into 100 ml Methanol (100 µg/mL).
- Telmisartan (TEL): Accurately weighed 80 mg of Telmisartan was dissolved into 100 ml Methanol (800 µg/mL).

Preparation of Sample solution

Take 10 Tablets and weigh the powder equivalent to 5 mg of Bisoprolol Fumarate and 40 mg of Telmisartan in 100 ml volumetric flask and make up the volume with methanol (50 + 400 µg/ml) and then sonicated for 10 minutes and filtered the solution. Pipette out 1 mL from above filtrate solution into the 10 mL volumetric flask and make up the volume with Mobile phase. (5 + 40 µg/mL)

Selection of Detection Wavelength

Analytical wavelength selection was done by the consideration of significant absorbance and from the detailed literature review. Working standards of Bisoprolol Fumarate (5 µg/mL) and Telmisartan (40 µg/mL) were prepared in Mobile phase were scanned in UV between 200 to 400 nm and the observed spectra were overlapped. Wavelength was selected based on significant absorbance.

Figure 3: Overlain UV spectra of BIS + TEL (5 + 40 µg/mL) in Mobile phase

Chromatographic conditions

The column used was Hibar ODS C₁₈ column (250 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 µm) under isocratic mode at a flow rate of 1.0 mL/min with UV detection at 230

nm. The mobile phase contained mixture of 10 mM Phosphate buffer: Acetonitrile in the ratio of (30: 70 v/v). The total run time of the method is 15 min, and the injection volume is 20 µL. The final

chromatographic conditions of the new method described are summarized in Table 1.

Forced degradation study

Accurately weighed equivalent weight of formulation powder which contains 5 mg Bisoprolol Fumarate + 40 mg Telmisartan and transferred in 100 ml volumetric flask and make up volume till mark with Mobile phase (50 + 400 $\mu\text{g/mL}$). Allow it to sonicate for 10 minutes and filter by using Whatman filter paper. The filtrate solution is used for Forced degradation study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 4: Chromatogram of BIS + TEL (1 + 8 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) under Optimized conditions

Table 2: Optimized Chromatographic conditions

Stationary phase	Hibar ODS C ₁₈ (250 mm \times 4.6 mm, 5 μm)
Pump mode	Isocratic
Mobile phase	Acetonitrile: 10 mM KH ₂ PO ₄ buffer (70: 30, v/v)
Column temperature	Ambient
Flow rate	1.0 mL/min
Detection wavelength	230 nm
Injection volume	20 μL
Run time	15 min
Retention time	BIS (5.715 min), TEL (3.205 min)
Diluent	Initial: MeOH Final: Mobile phase

Method Validation

The validation of method can be performed as per ICH guideline. The parameters assessed were system suitability parameters, specificity,

Method development and optimization

Stability-indicating RP-HPLC method was developed for quantitative estimation of Bisoprolol Fumarate and Telmisartan in Tablet dosage form. The separation was achieved by using Hibar ODS C₁₈ column (250 mm \times 4.6 mm, 5 μm) and 10 mM Phosphate buffer: Acetonitrile (30: 70 v/v) as mobile phase at a flow rate of 1.0 mL/min and detection wavelength was 230 nm. The R_t was found to be 5.715 min for Bisoprolol Fumarate and 3.205 min for Telmisartan.

linearity, precision, accuracy, LOD, LOQ and robustness.

System suitability

The system suitability tests were performed using solution of BIS + TEL (1 + 8 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) and was injected three times with replicates for determination of retention time, symmetry factor, resolution, theoretical plates, and RSD.

Table 3: System suitability parameters

Parameters (n=3)	BIS	RS D	TEL	RS D
Retention time	5.72 \pm 0.04	0.66	3.22 \pm 0.03	0.80
Tailing factor	1.43 \pm 0.01	0.94	1.18 \pm 0.01	0.77
Theoretical plates	3825.15 \pm 34.23	0.90	3317.24 \pm 28.10	0.85
Resolution	3.28 \pm 0.03			0.77

Linearity

Linearity test solutions for the assay method were prepared at 5 concentration levels from the of

concentration (1+8, 2+16, 3+24, 4+32, and 5+40 µg/mL). The peak areas vs concentration data were evaluated by linear regression analysis.

Figure 5: Calibration curve of BIS for Linearity study

Figure 6: Calibration curve of TEL for Linearity study

Figure 7: Overlain chromatogram of BIS and TEL from Linearity studies

Table 4: Linearity data of BIS

Sr. no.	Concentration (µg/mL)				
	1	2	3	4	5
1.	144293	282712	420579	562310	695231
2.	145454	283637	422284	563889	696758
3.	146947	286419	423213	564735	697297
4.	148104	288838	426186	567497	699193
5.	149442	288979	428548	568479	699561

Mean	146848	286117	424162	565382	697608
SD	2048.62	2890.96	3185.87	2556.83	1788.56
%RSD	1.40	1.01	0.75	0.45	0.26

(n=5)

Table 5: Linearity data of TEL

Sr. no.	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)				
	8	16	24	32	40
1.	1190349	2489512	3785601	5032413	6566498
2.	1173165	2456133	3722147	5002478	6542357
3.	1182487	2446856	3741237	5023478	6556743
4.	1204568	2485741	3734121	5051664	6551027
5.	1165984	2431875	3714145	5042416	6548141
Mean	1183311	2462023	3739450	5030490	6552953
SD	15043.59	24959.07	27844.40	18895.14	9178.39
%RSD	1.27	1.01	0.74	0.38	0.14

(n=5)

Precision

The precision of the method was evaluated in terms of repeatability of Bisoprolol Fumarate and Telmisartan test sample preparation and calculating the relative standard deviation (RSD)

of the assay (Intraday). Intermediate precision of the method was checked by having another person perform the same procedure on a different day (Interday) under the same experimental conditions.

Table 6: Interday and Intraday precision data of BIS

Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Inter-day		Intra-day	
	Mean \pm SD	% RSD	Mean \pm SD	% RSD
1	147702 \pm 1971.43	1.33	143291 \pm 1137.95	0.79
3	425782 \pm 4007.90	0.94	426499 \pm 2563.79	0.60
5	696390 \pm 5177.48	0.74	693843 \pm 2203.43	0.31

(n=3)

Table 7: Interday and Intraday precision data of TEL

Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Inter-day		Intra-day	
	Mean \pm SD	% RSD	Mean \pm SD	% RSD
8	1192303 \pm 14716.91	1.23	1126929 \pm 11547.11	1.02
24	3740180 \pm 39414.80	1.05	3765531 \pm 25234.24	0.67
40	6550288 \pm 59693.97	0.91	6661831 \pm 13744.46	0.21

(n=3)

Accuracy

An accuracy study was performed by adding known amounts of Bisoprolol Fumarate and Telmisartan to the sample preparation. The actual and measured concentrations were compared. Recovery of the method was evaluated at 3 different concentration levels (corresponding to

50, 100, and 150% of the test preparation concentration). For each concentration level, 3 sets were prepared and injected in duplicate.

Table 8: Recovery data of BIS and TEL

Drug	Level of Spiking	Amount of Sample (mg)	Amount spiked (µg/mL)	Amount recovered (µg/mL)	% Mean Recovery ± SD
BIS	Unspiked	10	-	-	-
	50%	10	1	0.98±0.01	98.00±1.00
	100%	10	2	1.97±0.02	98.67±0.76
	150%	10	3	2.97±0.02	99.00±0.67
TEL	Unspiked	80	-	-	-
	50%	80	8	7.93±0.06	99.08±0.75
	100%	80	16	15.86±0.07	99.15±0.44
	150%	80	24	23.86±0.09	99.43±0.39

(n=3)

Solvent stability

Solvent stability was determined by injecting the same solution at optimized chromatographic condition at 3 different time intervals that is 0 h, 8 h and 24 h. Mixture of Bisoprolol Fumarate + TEL (2 + 16 µg/mL) was injected at optimized chromatographic condition at selected time interval and peak area was observed.

Table 9: Solvent stability data of BIS and TEL

Time (h)	Area	
	BIS	TEL
0	283667	2427828
8	285708	2438351

24	288359	2441563
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LOD and LOQ

LOD and LOQ were determined by two methods,

- Visual inspection
- Statistical method by utilization of repeatability data

$$LOD = 3.3 \times \frac{\sigma}{S}$$

$$LOQ = 10 \times \frac{\sigma}{S}$$

where,

σ = Standard deviation of response

S = Slope of the calibration curve

Figure 8: LOD for BIS + TEL (100 + 800 ng/mL) by Visual inspection**Table 10: LOD and LOQ data of BIS and TEL by Statistical calculation**

Drug	LOD (µg/mL)	LOQ (µg/mL)
BIS	0.06	0.19
TEL	0.61	1.85

Robustness**Table 11: Robustness data of BIS and TEL**

Parameters	Level of Changes	Observation	
		BIS	TEL

The robustness study was performed to evaluate the influence of small but deliberate variations in the chromatographic conditions. The factors chosen for this study were the flow rate (± 0.1 mL/min), mobile phase composition acetonitrile: phosphate buffer (± 5 mL, v/v).

		Peak Area	%RSD	Peak Area	%RSD
Flow rate	0.9 mL/min	691162	0.33	6526631	0.39
	1.0 mL/min	695231		6566498	
	1.1 mL/min	695176		6574379	
Composition of Mobile Phase	75: 25 v/v	699095	1.08	6588679	1.20
	70: 30 v/v	695231		6566498	
	65: 35 v/v	684613		6442465	

Assay

Table 12: Assay data of BIS and TEL Formulation

Drug	BIS	TEL
Amount Taken ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	5	40

Amount Found ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	4.90 \pm 0.03	39.48 \pm 0.45
%Assay	98.07 \pm 0.51	98.70 \pm 1.14

(n=3 determinations at each level)

Figure 9: Chromatogram of Tablet Formulation

Forced degradation study

Sample mixture of Bisoprolol Fumarate and Telmisartan were exposed in different conditions and performed the chromatographic analysis of degradants.

- 1) Acidic Degradation: Acidic degradation was performed by heating the drug content in 0.1 N HCl at 60°C for 1 h and then the mixture was neutralized.
- 2) Alkaline Degradation: Alkaline degradation was performed by heating the drug content in 0.1 N NaOH at 60°C for 1 h and then the mixture was neutralized.
- 3) Oxidative Degradation: The oxidation degradation was performed by heating the drug content in 3% (w/v) H₂O₂ at 60°C for 1 h.
- 4) Thermal Degradation: Thermal degradation was performed by heating the solid drug at 60°C for 3 h.

Figure 10: Chromatogram of Treated sample with 0.1 N HCl (acid hydrolysis)

Figure 11: Chromatogram of Treated sample with 0.1 N NaOH (base hydrolysis)

Figure 12: Chromatogram of Treated sample with 3% (w/v) H₂O₂ (oxidative degradation)

Table 13: Summary of Forced degradation study

Stress condition	Type of sample	Area		%Degradation	
		BIS	TEL	BIS	TEL
Acid hydrolysis	Control	423154	4311384	14.28	14.92
	Treated	362728	3668341		
Base hydrolysis	Control	427101	4478825	13.82	14.18
	Treated	368064	3843679		
Oxidative degradation	Control	503581	5582653	11.22	11.75
	Treated	447103	4926537		
Thermal degradation	Standard	699561	6548141	10.27	10.94
	Treated	627715	5831531		

Control= Sample prepared without imposing to stress conditions

Treated= Sample prepared with stress conditions

Table 14: Summary of validation parameters

Parameter	Result	
	BIS	TEL
Linearity and Range	0.999 (1-5 µg/mL)	0.999 (8-40 µg/mL)
Repeatability (RSD)	1.40-0.26	1.27-0.14
Interday precision (RSD)	1.33-0.74	1.23-0.91
Intraday precision (RSD)	0.79-0.31	1.02-0.21
%Recovery	99.00-98.00	98.08-99.43
Specificity	Specific	Specific
Sensitivity	Sensitive	Sensitive
Robustness	Robust	Robust

CONCLUSIONS

In this research, a new, simple, precise, accurate, and robust stability indicating RP-HPLC method was developed for quantification of Bisoprolol Fumarate and Telmisartan in combined marketed tablet formulation. The proposed method is capable to separate and quantify the components from their combination. The proposed was able to detect the degradants of both drugs. Results of the validation parameters and assay were in an acceptable range. Hence, it can be employed in routine assay of Bisoprolol Fumarate and Telmisartan in combined formulation.

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Conflict Of Interest

All authors declare no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

1. Snehal P, Ashpak T, Sunil M, Shubhada P: Simultaneous Determination of Bisoprolol Fumarate and Telmisartan by Area under Curve UV Spectrophotometric Method. Int. J. Pharm. Pharma. Res. 2020; 18(2):147-156.
2. Sattar OI, Abuseada HH, Ramzy S, Abuelwafa MM: Three spectrophotometric quantitative analysis of bisoprolol fumarate and telmisartan in fixed-dose combination utilizing ratio spectra manipulation methods. Scientific Reports 2024; 14(1):22899.
3. Barge VU, Gaikwad RB, Chaudhari FM, Kande T: Development and Validation of Analytical Method for Simultaneous Estimation of Bisoprolol Fumarate and Telmisartan by Using RP HPLC Method. Int. J. Pharm. Clinical Res. 2018; 10(8):219-23.
4. Shivani R, Dhopate, LR, Gandhi, NS Bhajipale: Development and Validation Of RP-HPLC Method For Simultaneous Estimation of Bisoprolol Fumarate and Telmisartan in Pharmaceutical Formulation. Int. J. Res. Ana. Rev. 2022; 9(2):178-186.
5. Chaudhari AR, Raut MA, Gabhane KB, Salode VL, Barde LN: Development and Validation Of RP-HPLC Method For Simultaneous Estimation of Bisoprolol Fumarate and Telmisartan in Bulk and Pharmaceutical Formulation. Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research 2022; 9(8): 766-774.
6. Snehal P, Ashpak T, Sunil M, Shubhada P: Development and validation of RP-HPLC method for the simultaneous estimation of bisoprolol fumarate and telmisartan from pharmaceutical formulations. Int. J. Pharm. Ana. Res. 2020; 9(2):129-136.
7. Gunjal S, Jain H, Sankaran S, Yadav S: High-performance thin-layer chromatography-based

- methodology for simultaneous estimation of bisoprolol fumarate and telmisartan. JPC–Journal of Planar Chromatography–Modern TLC 2024; 37(2):161-8.
8. Bhavsar A, Tandel D, Patel K, Parmar R, Patel G, Gandhi T: DoE assisted, stability indicating HPTLC method development and validation for concurrent determination of Telmisartan and Bisoprolol fumarate in tablet dosage form. Essential Chem 2025; 2(1):1-6.
 9. Chauhan A, Bharti MB, Chauhan P: Analytical Method Development and Validation: A Concise Review. J. Anal. Bioanal. Tech. 2015; 6(1):1-5.
 10. Doltade M, Saudagar R: Analytical Method Development and Validation: A Review. J. Drug Delivery Thera. 2019; 9(3):563-570.
 11. Mr. Gorhe S G, Miss. Pawar G R: A Review on High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC). Int. J. of Adv. Sci. Res. Eng. Trends 2018; 3(1):5-9.
 12. Manjiri S, Dr. Satish K, Dr. Arunabha M, Dr. N Jyothi: A Review on HPLC Method Development and Validation. EPRA Int. J. Res. Development 2021; 6(10):92-96.
 13. Yadav V and Bharkatiya M: A Review on HPLC Method Development and Validation. Res. J. Life Sci. 2017; 2(6):166-178.
 14. Pallavi NP: HPLC Method Development - A Review. J. Pharm. Res. Edu. 2017; 2(1):243-260.
 15. Blessy M: Development of forced degradation and stability indicating studies of drugs-A review. J. Pharm. Anal. 2014; 4:159- 165.
 16. Brummer DH: How to approach a forced degradation study. Life Sci Tech Bull 2011; 31:1-4.
 17. Iram F: Forced Degradation Studies. J. Anal. Pharm. Res. 2016 3:73.
 18. Klick S, Muijselaar PG, Waterval J, Eichinger T, Korn C, et al.: Toward a Generic Approach for Stress Testing of Drug Substances and Drug Products. Pharm. Tech. 2000; 29(2):48-57.
 19. ICH Q2A Text on validation of analytical procedure, International conference on harmonization. Tripartite guideline 1994; 1-5.
 20. ICH Q2B Validation of analytical procedure: methodology, International conference on harmonization. Tripartite guideline 1994; 1-10.

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